

TABLE I—ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Sl. No.	Compound	%Metal		μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	
1.	CoI ₂ (Py) ₂	11.59 (11.66)	10.97 (11.09)	4.9
2.	CoL ₂ (β -Pic) ₂	11.00 (11.09)	10.48 (10.54)	5.1
3.	CoL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	10.97 (11.09)	10.52 (10.54)	4.9
4.	CoL ₂ (Q) ₂	9.68 (9.73)	9.20 (9.25)	4.9
5.	CoL ₂ (Pip) ₂	11.35 (11.39)	10.73 (10.83)	4.9
6.	CoL ₂ (2,6-Lut) ₂	10.48 (10.57)	10.02 (10.05)	5.0
7.	CoL ₂ (Quin) ₂	9.27 (9.30)	8.76 (8.84)	4.8
8.	CoL ₂ (4-AP) ₂	10.94 (11.01)	10.38 (10.48)	4.9
9.	CoL ₂ (Mor) ₂	11.26 (11.30)	10.63 (10.75)	4.9
10.	CoL ₂ , <i>o</i> -PhDA	12.38 (12.94)	12.27 (12.31)	4.9
11.	CoL ₂ ,1,10-Phe	11.08 (11.17)	10.58 (10.62)	5.0
12.	CoL ₂ ,2-2'-bipy	11.68 (11.71)	11.10 (11.13)	5.0
13.	CdL ₂ (Py) ₂	19.95 (20.12)	9.97 (10.02)	—
14.	CdL ₂ (β -Pic) ₂	19.17 (19.23)	9.51 (9.58)	—
15.	CdL ₂ (γ -Pic) ₂	19.15 (19.23)	9.48 (9.58)	—
16.	CdL ₂ (Q) ₂	16.94 (17.07)	8.43 (8.50)	—
17.	CdL ₂ (2,6-Lut) ₂	18.28 (18.41)	9.12 (9.17)	—
18.	CdL ₂ (Pip) ₂	19.68 (19.70)	9.76 (9.81)	—
19.	CdL ₂ , <i>o</i> -PhDA	22.04 (22.10)	10.97 (11.01)	—

Py = pyridine, β -Pic = β -picoline, γ -Pic = γ -picoline, Q = quinoline, Pip = piperidine, 2,6-Lut = 2,6-lutidine, Quin = quinaldine, 4-AP = 4-amino-pyridine, Mor = morpholine, *o*-PhDA = *o*-phenylenediamine, 1,10-Phe = 1,10-phenanthroline, 2-2'-bipy = 2-2'-bipyridine.

coordinated water molecules and its conspicuous absence in the mixed ligand complexes support the coordination of nitrogen donor ligands to the metal ions.

In the electronic spectra, the cobalt(II) complexes in DMF solution give rise to two absorption bands with maxima around 8.6 and 19.7 kK region which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transitions. These absorption bands along with its magnetic moment values indicate a high-spin octahedral configuration for cobalt(II) complexes.

All the cadmium(II) complexes are six-coordinated on the basis of analysis, conductance and ir spectral studies.

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Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) with Schiff Base Derived from Bis-*p*-(Aminophenyl) Sulphide and 2-Acetyl Thiophene Glyoxal

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IN continuation to our work¹⁻³ on Schiff base complexes, present note describes the preparation and characterisation of complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) with the Schiff base (I). Conductance, magnetic moment, electronic and infrared spectra of the complexes have been studied.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by taking the bis-*p*-(aminophenyl) sulphide and 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal in dioxane in equimolar quantities and refluxing for about 1 hr. The refluxed mass was poured into ice cold water when an orange coloured mass separated out. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator and recrystallised from ethanol. Bright orange coloured fine crystals, m.p. 186°, were obtained.

A general procedure was adopted to synthesise the complexes by mixing Co(II), Ni(II), Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) chloride (10 m mole each) in 25 ml acetone with 10 m mole of the ligand separately. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min and concentrated in a vacuum desiccator, yielding the coloured crystalline material. The crystals were washed with ether and dried.

The analysis of carbon, nitrogen and sulphur were done at the micro analytical section of C. D. R. I., Lucknow. The chloride was estimated by Volhard's method. The metal contents in all

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NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA, FORMULAE AND OTHER PROPERTIES OF THE COMPLEXES.

Complex	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis %					# _{eff} B.M.
			M	C	N	S	Cl	
[CoLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	grey	192d	12.47 (12.12)*	43.20 (44.45)	5.38 (5.76)	13.38 (13.17)	14.90 (14.61)	4.89
[NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	dark green	167d	12.32 (12.08)	45.50 (44.47)	5.60 (5.76)	13.42 (13.17)	14.87 (14.60)	2.98
[CrL ₂]Cl ₂	black	198d	6.52 (6.23)	50.20 (51.76)	6.92 (6.71)	15.58 (15.33)	13.00 (12.76)	3.86
[MnL ₂]Cl ₂	grey	200d	6.60 (6.56)	51.42 (51.58)	6.70 (6.68)	14.20 (14.09)	12.76 (12.71)	4.80
[FeL ₂]Cl ₂	dark	208d	6.90 (6.66)	50.30 (51.53)	6.43 (6.67)	15.41 (15.26)	12.56 (12.30)	5.84

* Figures within the parentheses are Calcd. values ; L = C₁₀H₁₄N₂S₂O ; d = decomposed.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA AND LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Complex	Bands cm ⁻¹	Assignments	10 Dq cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	β	L.F.S.E. Kcals/mole
[CoLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	9700 17680 22000	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	—	843	0.75	13.86
[NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	10000 17756 26030	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)	10000	896	0.82	34.28
[CrL ₂]Cl ₂	14250 18400 23270 38400	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ E _g (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	18400	760	0.82	31.54
[MnL ₂]Cl ₂	17980 19200 11000	⁶ B _{1g} → ⁶ T _{2g} → ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁶ B _{2g} → ⁶ E _g	17980	832	0.73	30.82
[FeL ₂]Cl ₂	29580 11780 19380 27010	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (G) → ⁴ T _{2g} (G) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)	11780	736	0.56	—

TABLE 3—IR SPECTRA (cm⁻¹)

L	[Co(LCl ₂ .H ₂ O)]	[NiLCl ₂ .H ₂ O]	[CrL ₂]Cl ₂	[MnL ₂]Cl ₂	[FeL ₂]Cl ₂	Tentative assignments
1260(w)	1245(w)	1246(w)	1220(w)	1220(w)	1230(w)	ν(C=S)
1650(s)	1630(s)	1635(s)	1590(s)	1610(s)	1610(s)	ν(CH=N)
1700(s)	1675(s)	1680(s)	1660(s)	1660(s)	1655(s)	ν(C=O)
—	485(m)	490(m)	460(m)	545(m)	540(m)	ν(M-O)
—	470(m)	475(m)	480(m)	470(m)	460(m)	ν(M-N)
—	350(s)	355(s)	375(s)	330(s)	325(s)	ν(M-S)
—	230(m)	275(m)	—	—	—	ν(M-Cl)

s = strong, m = medium and w = weak.

these complexes were estimated by complexometric titrations with EDTA⁴⁻. The physical measurements viz, magnetic susceptibility (Gouy's balance), infrared spectra (Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model-521, fitted with NaCl and KBr optics), absorption spectra (UNICAM SP-500 spectrophotometer) and molar conductance (Phillips conductivity bridge, type LBRB) were recorded at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The complexes under investigation are listed in Table 1 along with their colour, analysis and other properties. The decomposition temperatures

indicate that the complexes are thermally stable. The values of observed magnetic moments show the paramagnetic nature of the chelates and are in agreement with the generally accepted values for high spin octahedral complexes, thus forming sp³d² type of bonding. The molar conductance of these complexes in DMF at 10⁻³ M indicates the non-electrolytic nature of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes and univalent nature of Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) complexes.

The electronic spectra (Table 2) of Co(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III) complexes show three bands appearing at 9700 cm⁻¹ [⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴T_{2g} (F)], 17580 cm⁻¹ [⁴T_{1g} (F) → ⁴A_{2g} (F)], 22000 cm⁻¹ [⁴T_{1g} (F) →

${}^4T_{1g}(P)$, 10000 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$], 17756 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$], 26030 cm^{-1} [${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$] and 11780 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$], 19380 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$], 27010 cm^{-1} [${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$], respectively. The complexes of Cr(III) and Mn(III) show four bands in their electronic spectra appearing at 14250 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3E_g$], 18400 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$], 23270 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$], 38400 cm^{-1} [${}^4A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$] and 11000 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6B_{2g}$], 13200 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$], 17980 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$], 29280 cm^{-1} [${}^6B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^6E_g$], respectively. The values of β of these complexes indicate the partial covalent character of the metal-ligand bond.

Infrared spectral data for the ligand and its complexes are given in Table 3. $\nu(C=N)$, $\nu(CH=N)$ and $\nu(C=O)$ are lowered on complex formation by 15 to 45 units indicating that these groups are participating in chelation. Bands appearing at 250 cm^{-1} and 275 cm^{-1} in Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, respectively are assignable to metal-chlorine stretching mode⁶.

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Azo Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of Some Organic Acids with *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-Naphthol

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A series of mixed ligand adducts of alkali metal salts of different organic acids with *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol, of the general formula

ML.OHBAN (M = Li, Na or K; L = deprotonated organic acids; 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8-hydroxyquinoline, *o*-nitrophenol, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde; OHBAN = *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol), have been synthesised. The adducts have been judged by their analytical results and infrared spectra, and this throws light on the fact that one molecule of alkali metal salt of organic acid combines with one molecule of ligand OHBAN, suggesting coordination number five or six for the metal atom.

Experimental

The ligand OHBAN was prepared by standard method¹, m.p. 194°. All the alkali metal salts used were prepared in 95% ethanol.

The general method of preparation was to take the hot absolute alcoholic solution of OHBAN and to add to it the alkali metal salts of organic acids in mono-molecular ratio. The whole mixture in solution was refluxed over water bath with stirring for about 1 hr. The solution, on keeping, yielded crystalline solid adducts. The crystals were filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts are stable when stored under dry condition e.g. in a desiccator. All the complexes are coloured (green, dark violet or brown). The compounds are thermally stable. When heated, they undergo a decomposition at a temperature higher than the melting point of the ligand. The adducts break on heating to form the simple salts and ligand, and this indicates that the bonding in these compounds is not strong. The colour, melting or decomposition temperatures and analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1.

The presence of two -OH groups in the *o, o'* positions to the azo group may increase the coordinating capacity of -N=N- group. It also suggests the possibility of intra-molecular hydrogen bonding due to which the metal is complexed in cyclic form.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Melting / Decomp. temp. °C	Found (%)				Calcd. (%)			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
OHBAN=L	Deep violet	194 m	72.69	4.55	10.61	—	72.72	4.54	10.60	—
Na1N2N.L	Dark violet	220 d	68.14	3.89	8.95	5.16	68.00	3.92	9.15	5.01
K1N2N.L	Dark violet	210 d	65.51	3.69	8.39	8.85	65.78	3.79	8.84	8.21
Na8HQ.L	Deep brown	250 d	70.48	4.10	9.51	5.09	70.40	4.06	9.48	5.19
K8HQ.L	Deep brown	215 d	67.92	3.94	9.48	8.14	68.00	3.92	9.35	8.50
NaONP.L	Green	233 d	62.09	3.81	9.95	5.40	62.12	3.76	9.88	5.41
KONP.L	Green	212 d	60.15	3.59	9.68	8.21	60.00	3.62	9.52	8.84
Na2H3NA.L	Brownish green	295 d	68.42	4.15	6.24	4.69	68.35	4.22	5.90	4.85
K2H3NA.L	Brownish green	290 d	66.42	3.91	6.11	7.59	66.12	3.88	5.71	8.00
Kacac.L	Green	208 d	62.92	4.45	5.82	9.95	62.68	4.72	6.96	9.70
Na.anth.L	Deep red	220 d	65.41	4.04	9.99	5.04	65.24	4.25	9.90	5.43
K.anth.L	Green	210 d	62.56	4.22	9.79	8.22	62.87	4.10	9.57	8.88
NaSalH.L	Brown	255 d	67.82	4.09	6.91	5.31	67.64	4.16	6.86	5.62
KSalH.L	Brown	242 d	64.92	4.12	6.98	8.75	65.10	4.00	6.60	9.20

OHBAN = *o*-hydroxybenzeneazo-2-naphthol, 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline, ONP = *o*-nitrophenol, 2H3NA = 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, acac = acetylacetone, anth = anthranilic acid, SalH = salicylaldehyde.